

Figure S145. Time series of monthly (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean bi-weekly NH_3 concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all AMoN and NAPS stations. Note that native AMoN units were kept as insufficient information was available from the network to convert to VMR units.

Figure S153. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean daily $\text{PM}_{2.5}\text{-NH}_4$ concentration ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CSN and NAPS stations.

Figure S160. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean weekly NH_4^+ concentration in precipitation ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and (c) NMB, (c) FAC2, and (d) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.

Figure S164. Time series of **monthly** (a) observed mean and (b) predicted mean weekly NH_4^+ wet deposition ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and (c) NMB, (d) FAC2, and (e) R statistics for 2013, 2014, 2015, and 2016 for all CAPMoN and NADP stations.